

THE PROBLEMS OF USING THE GOOGLE CLASSROOM APPLICATION IN THE ONLINE LEARNING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to find out The Problems of Using Google Classroom at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere and find solutions to problems in using Google classroom at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere. The type of research used in this research is qualitative and the data collection techniques used are observation and interviews. There were 18 informants in this research, namely 1 principal, 3 teachers, and 15 students at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere. The results of this study are Problems in Using the Google Classroom Application at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere experienced by teachers or students. The first obstacle faced by teachers is that not all students have cellphones or laptops. The second obstacle is network problems and running out of internet quota. While the obstacles experienced by students, the first obstacle is the internet network problem. The second obstacle is running out of internet quota, the third obstacle is lack of understanding of the material, The fourth obstacle is feeling full. Solutions made to overcome the problem of using Google Classroom students are advised to be able to use school Wi-Fi or the school can work with communication service providers. Students who not understand the material can ask the teacher via WhatsApp or discuss with friends, and can look for additional subject-related material on the internet or read it back in textbooks. Teachers must be creative and innovative.

INTRODUCTION

Online learning is basically distance learning via the internet. In this day and age, it is no stranger to the internet. Today, internet is the main source for everyone to access to everything they need. Online learning has been carried out during the last 3 years, due to the emergence of a virus that entered Indonesia, namely Covid-19. Covid-19 entered Indonesia on March 2, 2020 (Decree of Ministry of Education and Culture Number 15 of 2020 concerning Implementation of Learning from Home during the Emergency Period for the Spread of Covid-19). This virus requires the government to implement a policy, namely limiting all activities carried out at home, including access to education. In that way students and teachers can take advantage of technology as a learning medium, one of which is by using learning applications of Google Classroom.

The Google Classroom application is currently one of the online learning media that is widely used in schools for the teaching and learning process (Farida, 2021). Its various functions can facilitate the teaching and learning process of students and teachers through networks or online. Teachers can provide material to students in the form of files, videos, or slides. In addition to providing material in the application, this application can also fill student attendance, collect assignments, and can discuss in class groups or ask teachers or friends. That way, the online teaching and learning process continues to run smoothly.

The Google Classroom application can be accessed anywhere and anytime using internet access (Putri et al., 2019) such as via a laptop, computer, tablet or smartphone and requires a good internet network. However, there are several obstacles that often arise when using the Google Classroom Application in the learning process, namely there are still students who do not have their own smartphones, so students do not submit assignments, students are late in submitting assignments, do not have internet quota, the network is not good, and students are fast feel bored. With this in mind, it can affect student learning outcomes.

The writer is interested in researching the learning process at Muhammadiyah Maumere High School in Using the Google Classroom Application, because there are several obstacles to students and teachers when carrying out online learning using the Google Classroom application. So that from the problems above, the writer conducted research at Muhammadiyah High School with the title "The Problem of Using Google Classroom Application in Learning Process at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere in 2022/2023 School Year". The research problem,

namely focusing on the problem during the process of learning to use the Google Classroom application in online learning process at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere. The formulation of the problem is as follows
What are the problems in implementing Google classroom at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere? What are the solutions to problems in using Google Classroom at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere?

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

The research method is one factor that is sufficient important in conducting a research, because basically research method is a scientific way to get data with specific purposes and uses. The research method is effort to discover, develop, and test something truth of knowledge by scientific means. Therefore, the method used in a study must be precise. Based on the approach and type of data used. This research is included in qualitative research so that it will produce descriptive data in the form of words. Data analyzed in it is descriptive and not in the form of numbers as in quantitative research. According to Sugiyono (2018) a qualitative research method is a method research used to examine the condition of natural objects, where researchers are as a key instrument, data collection techniques carried out by triangulation (combined), data analysis is inductive, and the results of qualitative research emphasize meaning more than generalizations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problems in Implementing Google Classroom at Muhammadiyah Senior High School

a. Constraints of Online/Google Classroom-Based Learning for Teachers

The teacher's role is very important in learning to dare because they have to guide and supervise children while studying at school. However, not a few teachers experience difficulties when accompanying students in participating in learning activities using the Google Classroom Application online. SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere carries out learning using the Google Classroom application as an Online learning method, learning activities are the principal's program, so that in the learning process students are required to study using the Google Classroom application, in the online learning process at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere it does not use the system via zoom, but with the teacher system only sending material or assignments in the Google Classroom application. In addition, the obstacles faced by teachers are that some students do not have learning media tools in the form of cellphones, laptops, or internet quota. So, that the online learning process cannot be said to be maximal. (*Interview of result English Teacher*).

The use of the google classroom application is only as a support in online learning, such as sending materials, assignments, and collecting assignments. However, in the implementation of online learning teacher has preparations before carrying out online learning, namely making classes first, then setting topics, KD, and then making material and then sending it to the Google Classroom application (*interview of result economics teacher*)

Some teachers are quite proficient in how to use the Google Classroom application which is used as an online learning medium at SMA Muhammadiyah. In addition, the obstacles faced by teachers are that some students do not have learning media, both cellphones and laptops, the online learning process requires internet quota, and the constraints of internet network instability. Meanwhile, not all students come from families that are financially sufficient to buy internet quota continuously, and almost all students come from villages where the internet network is still unstable and electricity is not evenly distributed, so it becomes an obstacle for students who live far from city (*interview of result Principal*).

In observations made by writer after interviewing informants, they found several problems faced by both teachers and students, namely the instability of internet connections on cellphones, considering that not all SMA Muhammadiyah were in the city center when distance learning was implemented.

Based on the observations, interviews above, it can be concluded that the first obstacle is that not all students have cellphones or laptops. The second obstacle is the difficulty of finding an internet network and running out of internet quota because not all students are in urban areas when implementing the online system during the Covid-19 pandemic and not all students come from families who are financially sufficient.

b. Student Constraints

The implementation of online learning at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic certainly brought various obstacles, namely obstacles for children as students. The main obstacle that is directly felt by students is the unavailability of complete facilities to support the learning process which is carried out online at home. This facility is really needed by students to support the smooth running of learning conducted at home online, for example facilities that are urgently needed at this time as online learning media, such as cellphones or laptops and internet network or adequate quota to make it easier for students to listen to the online learning process.

The difficulties currently faced by SMA Muhammadiyah students in online learning have various obstacles. The impact of online learning is that there are several needs needed such as online learning facilities, in the form of cellphones or laptops, internet quota, and internet network problems. However, at SMA Muhammadiyah, almost all students have cellphones, so that is not a major obstacle. However, the biggest obstacle experienced by SMA Muhammadiyah students was network problems because students had difficulty downloading material or opening the Google Classroom

application (*This is evidenced by the results of student interviews A1, A2, A3, A9, A12*).

Based on the results of the interview above, explaining that the constraints in online learning really make it difficult for students when they want to open the Google Classroom application, the network is less stable in sending assignments, the internet package runs out so that students have to rent wifi because they don't have enough money to buy internet quota, and download the material provided by the teacher because the normal internet connection is not very good. Obstacles in online learning are internet access which sometimes does not support the implementation of online learning, internet quota is too expensive which makes it difficult for students to participate in online learning activities.

In carrying out online learning at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere, they do not use an online learning system via zoom but the teacher only sends material or assignments to students, thus making students less understand of the material sent because there is no direct explanation from the teacher (*This was conveyed by students A14, A9, A6, A7*).

Based on the results of the interview above, it was explained that students had great difficulty in learning and did not understand the material provided by the teacher because it was only given in file form without any explanation from the teacher, because at SMA Muhammadiyah implementing online learning does not use the system via zoom so that students have difficulty understanding the material. This can affect student learning outcomes.

SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere is one of the schools that implements an online learning system, in which all learning activities are carried out at home during the pandemic. students must be very clever about activities at home so they are not boring. Students at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere are also known to experience difficulties in the form of feeling bored or bored with the learning system and also the life system they are living during a pandemic. (*This is supported by the student statement A7, A6, A14*).

From the statement above, it can be seen that while studying online at SMA Muhammadiyah students feel bored or bored because of the activities they are doing at home during the pandemic, without meeting face to face with the teacher, there is no interaction between classmates, and online learning is monotonous.

Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted by writer, the learning process at SMA Muhammadiyah experienced several problems for students. The first problem is the problem of the internet network. Sometimes there are some students who complain about not being able to send assignments, download materials, and errors in the application when they want to open it due to unstable network problems considering that not all students live in cities but live in villages that are constrained by the network. The second problems is running out of internet quota, almost

some students are late in submitting their assignments because of this problem.

The third problems is lack of understanding of the material, students have difficulty understanding online learning because this school does not carry out online learning via zoom but the teacher only sends material in the form of files or videos without any explanation from the teacher. This can affect student learning outcomes. The fourth problems are feeling bored, students doing activities at home during a pandemic makes students feel bored or bored, due to the absence of face-to-face meetings with teachers, no interaction between classmates, and monotonous online learning.

Solutions for Schools Regarding Problems in Using Google Classroom

Based on a Circular Letter (SE) issued by the government on March 18 2020, all indoor and outdoor activities in all sectors are temporarily suspended in order to reduce the spread of the corona, especially in the education sector. On March 24, 2020 the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia issued Circular Number 4 of 2020 concerning the Implementation of Education Policies in the Emergency Period of the Spread of Covid-19. The circular letter explains that the learning process is carried out at home through online/distance learning to provide a meaningful learning experience for students.

SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere is one of the schools that applies the distance learning method or online learning. While carrying out online learning, there are certainly obstacles, the same is true for teachers and students at SMA Muhammadiyah who have several obstacles. To overcome the problems that exist in online learning, the school principal provides an alternative solution for students who do not have cellphones or laptops to use laptops or school computers. *(As stated by the Mathematics Teacher, students A1, A5) .*

Based on the results of observations after the writer conducted interviews with informants, it can be concluded that students who do not have an internet quota can use the facilities provided by the school in the online learning process. Meanwhile, students who are late in submitting assignments can confirm with the subject teacher to be given additional time.

Discussion

Problems in Implementing Google Classroom at SMA Muhammadiyah

Based on observations made by writer in the use of Google Classroom learning media in online learning activities at SMA Muhammadiyah, there are several obstacles experienced by teachers and students when carrying out online learning. The first obstacle faced by teachers is that not all students have cell phones or laptops. The second obstacle is network problems and running out of internet quota. This is certainly an obstacle for teachers because students who are constrained by the network cannot carry out learning and submit assignments on time. This is what makes the teacher unable to carry out learning optimally. This is in

line with the research of Alim, et al (2019) this research states that Google Classroom is effectively used.

While the obstacles experienced by SMA Muhammadiyah students were several obstacles such as, the first obstacle was internet network problems. Sometimes there were some students who complained about not being able to send assignments, download material, and errors in the application when they wanted to open it due to network problems that were less stable. The second obstacle is running out of internet quota, almost some students are late in submitting their assignments because of this problem. The third obstacle is lack of understanding of the material. The fourth obstacle is feeling bored. Students doing activities at home during the pandemic make students feel bored or bored, due to the absence of face-to-face meetings with the teacher, no interaction between classmates, and monotonous online learning.

Solutions for Schools Regarding Problems in Using Google Classroom

Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted by writer regarding the efforts made to deal with the problems experienced in implementing online learning media for problems regarding network connections, that students often experience network constraint problems, namely by asking students to find a place that has a smooth network during the learning process. That online learning is a learning process that utilizes the internet network during the learning process. (Isman,2016)

The online learning process completely depends on a smooth internet network so that learning can be carried out properly. Another effort made by the school regarding students who have run out of internet quota and not all students come from families that are financially sufficient to buy internet quota continuously, can use school Wi-Fi or schools can work with communication service providers to provide credit subsidies to students, Students during the online learning process. Furthermore, for students who do not understand the material sent by the teacher, they can ask the teacher via WhatsApp or discuss with friends, and can search for additional subject-related material on the internet. Finally, teachers must be creative and innovative to make learning more interesting and increase students' interest in participating in online learning so students don't feel bored. Google Classroom is a good new innovation in learning because by using this application teachers and students get the advantage of easy access so they can study anywhere and anytime as long as they have an internet connection. Salam (2020).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the data analysis and discussion that has been carried out in the research and referring to the formulation of the problem and research objectives, the following conclusions are obtained:

Problems in using Google Classroom as a learning tool in the Covid-19 era at SMA Muhammadiyah Maumere, there are several obstacles experienced by teachers and students when implementing online learning. The first obstacle faced by teachers is that not all students have cell phones or laptops. The second obstacle is network problems and running out of internet quota. Thus, making students unable to submit assignments on time. This is what makes teachers unable to carry out online learning optimally.

While the constraints experienced by students, namely the first obstacle is internet network problems. Sometimes there are some students who complain about not being able to submit assignments, download material, and errors in applications when they want to open them due to network problems that are less stable. The second obstacle is running out of internet quota, almost some students are late in submitting their assignments because of this problem. The third obstacle is lack of understanding of the material. The fourth obstacle is feeling bored. Students doing activities at home during the pandemic make students feel bored or bored, due to the absence of face-to-face meetings with the teacher, no interaction between classmates, and monotonous online learning.

Solution for teachers can make to overcome the problems students experience in using Google Classroom media, namely: students are advised

to be able to use school wifi or schools can work with communication service providers to provide credit subsidies to students during the online learning process . Students who do not understand the material sent by the teacher can ask the teacher via WhatsApp or discuss with friends, and can look for additional subject-related material on the internet. Teachers must be creative and innovative to make learning more interesting and increase students' interest in participating in online learning so students don't feel bored.

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Ramadhan

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